

CONTEMPORARY AGRICULTURE
SAVREMENA POLJOPRIVREDA

The Serbian Journal of Agricultural Sciences
Srpski časopis za poljoprivredne nauke

Vol. 64, No. 1 - 2, Pp. 1 - 119, 2015.

www:Contemporary Agriculture
ISSN: 0350-1205 UDC: 63(497.1)(051)-"540.2"

University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Published by Faculty of Agriculture, Novi Sad

Original scientific paper

UDC: 612.664:599.735

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN HEMATOLOGICAL AND METABOLIC PARAMETERS IN COWS DURING EARLY LACTATION*

Zorana KOVAČEVIĆ[♦], Marko R. CINCOVIĆ, Branislava BELIĆ,
Dragica STOJANOVIĆ, Radojica ĐOKOVIĆ¹

Summary: Energy metabolism in cows was significantly altered in early lactation, there is an increased concentration of BHB and bilirubin, a decreased concentration of glucose. Metabolism of protein is also altered so that the concentration of total protein, albumin and urea lowest in the first week after parturition, but then slowly grew. In the peripartum period, especially on the day of calving and the first days of lactation cows have fewer red blood cells and a lower concentration of hemoglobin. There is a decline in the total number of leukocytes. The aim of this study is to determine link between blood count and parameters of metabolic status of cows in early lactation. The research was conducted on 40 Holstein-Friesian cows. Blood samples were taken in the first week after calving. According to the statistical analysis, it was noticed that there was not relation between the total number of leukocytes and the metabolic status of cows in early lactation. Also, it was noticed that cows with higher values of N:L ratio, lower hemoglobin concentration and smaller number of red blood cells had higher concentration of BHB, AST and TBIL and lower concentrations of ALB. Changes in the values of metabolic parameters in a function of hematological parameters were statistically significant. Based on the above, the link between blood count parameters that indicate inflammation and metabolic adaptations in cows in early lactation is demonstrated. In further research should examine the relationship between inflammatory and metabolic parameters.

Key words: blood count, metabolic status, cows.

INTRODUCTION

In lactating, dairy cows does not significantly affect the parameters of the white blood cells, or endocrine changes, peripartum stress and the development of infections significantly alter blood to the image of cows in the peripartum period. Of particular interest is the determination of total leukocytes, neutrophils, lymphocytes and neutrophils relation to the number of lymphocyte (N: L ratio). There is a decline in the total number of leukocytes in the peripartum period (Klinkon at al., 1999; Sattar and Mirza, 2009; Mirzadeh et al. 2010; Belic et al., 2011).

¹Zorana Kovačević, MSc, Teaching Assistant, Marko R. Cincović, DVM, PhD, Assistant Professor, Branislava Belić, DM, PhD, Associate Professor, Dragica Stojanović, DVM, PhD, Full Professor, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Veterinary Medicine, Squ. D. Obradovića 8, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia. Radojica Đoković, DVM, PhD, Full Professor, Faculty of Agronomy, Čačak, Serbia.

[♦]Corresponding author: Zorana Kovačević, e-mail: zoranakovacevic@yahoo.co.uk

*This paper is a part of scientific projects TR31062, Ministry of education and science, Republic of Serbia.

The ratio of neutrophils and lymphocytes (N: L ratio) is an important indicator of the health burden and stress of animals (Davis et al., 2008). This ratio in adult cattle is about 0.5: 1, while the value of the ratio N: L over 1 indicates that cows are loaded inflammation or other stressors (Latimer and Prasse, 2003). In the period around calving, acute stress and hypercortisolemia lead to an increase in the concentration of neutrophils, which leads to the increase in the neutrophil and lymphocyte (N: L) ratio is often more than 1 (Tornquist and Rigas, 2010). After adaptation to stressful conditions N: L ratio returns to the physiological level in the period 2-7 days (Lynch et al., 2010).

In the peripartum period, especially on the day of calving and the first days of lactation cows have fewer red blood cells and a lower concentration of hemoglobin (Klinkon et al., 1999; Sattar and Mirza, 2009; Mirzadeh et al. 2010; Belic et al., 2011). The emergence of anemia and decreased hemoglobin concentration with metabolic load and elevated concentrations of NEFA may predispose cows to the emergence of perinatal inflammation of the uterus (Belic et al., 2012). Ketosis in cows in the peripartum period has an impact on erythrocyte lineage that can show signs of anemia (Belic et al., 2010).

Energy metabolism in cows was significantly altered in early lactation, there is an increased concentration of BHB and bilirubin, a decreased concentration of glucose. This finding indicates the presence of negative energy balance and expressed ketogenesis. Metabolism of protein is also altered so that the concentration of total protein, albumin and urea lowest in the first week after parturition, but then slowly grew. This situation arises as a result of insufficient food consumption, but also loads of liver function and reduction of its synthetic capacity. This is confirmed by the hepatic profile, because the enzyme activity of ALT and AST and bilirubin, or significantly higher in the first or in the second week after parturition (Wathes et al., 2007). Negative energy balance and metabolic adaptation in early lactation are in relation with inflammation profile, blood profile and healthy status of cows (Sordillo et al, 2009; Cincović et al., 2012; Djokovic et al, 2014)

The aim of this study is to determine link between blood parameters as indicators of inflammation and parameters of metabolic status of cows in early lactation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The experiment was performed on 40 Holstein-Friesian cows. Cows were kept in equal environmental and technology condition. Blood samples were taken in the first week after calving.

We determined following hematological parameters: the total number of leukocytes, neutrophils:lymphocyte ratio (N:L), hemoglobin concentration and red blood cell count by using a Hemavet analyzer. Also, we determined following parameters of the metabolic profile in blood serum: beta-hydroxybutyrate (BHB), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), total bilirubin (TBIL) and albumin (ALB) by standard biochemical kits (Randox) using a Rayto spectrophotometer.

For statistical analysis cows were classified according to the hematological parameters into quartiles (four groups). We examined the differences in metabolite concentrations between the four mentioned groups by using ANOVA model with post-hoc LSD test. We examined the significance of changes in the trend function of the concentration of metabolites in the blood values by using the Cochran-Armitage test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results show that there is no significant relation ($P>0.05$) between the total number of leukocytes and the metabolic status of cows in early lactation. This results are presented in Table 1. Cows with higher values of neutrophils:lymphocyte ratio (N: L), lower hemoglobin concentration and smaller number of red blood cells have a higher concentration of BHB, AST and TBIL and lower concentrations of ALB. Changes in the values of metabolic parameters in a function of hematological parameters was statistically significant ($P<0.05$) and it is presented in Table 2, 3 and 4. Wathes et al. (2007) reported that in early lactation, there is an increased concentration of BHB, bilirubin, albumin and AST what is similar with our results. Also, our results are matched with group of authors Klinkon et al. (1999), Sattar and Mirza (2009), Mirzadeh et al. (2010), Belic et al. (2011), who claimed that in the peripartum period, cows have fewer red blood cells, lower concentration of hemoglobin and decline in the total number of leukocytes.

That fact was noticed in our examination according to the statistical analysis is that there was not relation between the total number of leukocytes and the metabolic status of cows in early lactation. Also, it was noticed that

cows with higher values of N:L ratio, lower hemoglobin concentration and smaller number of red blood cells had higher concentration of BHB, AST and TBIL and lower concentrations of ALB.

Table 1. Influence of total leukocytes number to metabolic status of cows

Total number of leukocytes	BHB mmol/l	AST IU/l	TBIL μ mol/l	ALB g/l
<25	0,8 \pm 0,12 ^a	111,5 \pm 12,14 ^a	7,5 \pm 2,4 ^a	63,5 \pm 2,1 ^a
25-50	0,7 \pm 0,14 ^a	108,8 \pm 13,11 ^a	6,9 \pm 2,9 ^a	59,9 \pm 2,6 ^b
51-75	0,9 \pm 0,11 ^b	105,6 \pm 15,1 ^a	8,1 \pm 2,5 ^a	63,4 \pm 2,4 ^a
>75	0,7 \pm 0,14 ^a	114,4 \pm 12,18 ^a	7,8 \pm 3,01 ^a	61,7 \pm 2,2 ^a
Trend	NS	NS	NS	NS

^{a,b} Values with different superscripts significantly differ (P<0.05).

Table 2. Influence of the N:L ratio to metabolic status of cows

N:L	BHB mmol/l	AST IU/l	TBIL μ mol/l	ALB g/l
<25	0,81 \pm 0,08 ^a	98,5 \pm 9,9 ^a	5,8 \pm 2,6 ^a	62,1 \pm 2,15 ^a
25-50	0,88 \pm 0,1 ^b	104,4 \pm 8,9 ^b	6,5 \pm 2 ^a	61,5 \pm 2,2 ^a
51-75	0,95 \pm 0,09 ^b	111,1 \pm 9,9 ^b	7,7 \pm 2,01 ^a	59,8 \pm 2,1 ^b
>75	1,14 \pm 0,11 ^c	118,8 \pm 11,14 ^c	8,99 \pm 1,8 ^b	57,6 \pm 2,5 ^b
Trend	<0,01	<0,01	<0,01	<0,01

^{a,b} Values with different superscripts significantly differ (P<0.05).

Table 3. Influence of the hemoglobin concentration to metabolic status of cows

HGB	BHB mmol/l	AST IU/l	TBIL μ mol/l	ALB g/l
<25	1,11 \pm 0,12 ^a	116,7 \pm 10,1 ^a	7,9 \pm 1,9 ^a	59,1 \pm 2,2 ^a
25-50	0,8 \pm 0,11 ^b	103,6 \pm 9,5 ^b	5,6 \pm 2,05 ^b	62,5 \pm 2,1 ^b
51-75	0,6 \pm 0,09 ^c	107,4 \pm 9,3 ^b	5,8 \pm 2,1 ^b	63,3 \pm 2,5 ^b
>75	0,7 \pm 0,12 ^c	102,5 \pm 9,5 ^b	5,7 \pm 2,17 ^b	63,5 \pm 2,4 ^b
Trend	<0,01	<0,05	<0,05	NS

Table 4. Influence of the number of red blood cells to metabolic status of cows

Number of erythrocytes	BHB mmol/l	AST IU/l	TBIL μ mol/l	ALB g/l
<25	0,99 \pm 0,09 ^a	115,5 \pm 10,3 ^a	7,5 \pm 1,8 ^a	59,2 \pm 2,01 ^a
25-50	0,75 \pm 0,1 ^b	111,1 \pm 11,1 ^a	5,8 \pm 1,6 ^b	60,5 \pm 2,1 ^b
51-75	0,8 \pm 0,12 ^b	99,9 \pm 12,2 ^b	5,1 \pm 2,1 ^b	62,5 \pm 2,05 ^b
>75	0,73 \pm 0,11 ^b	102,3 \pm 9,9 ^b	5,2 \pm 2,2 ^b	63,1 \pm 2,2 ^b
Trend	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05

^{a,b} Values with different superscripts significantly differ (P<0.05).

CONCLUSION

According to the statistical analysis, it was noticed that there was not relation between the total number of leukocytes and the metabolic status of cows in early lactation. Also, it was noticed that cows with higher values of N:L ratio, lower hemoglobin concentration and smaller number of red blood cells had higher concentration of BHB, AST and TBIL and lower concentrations of ALB. Changes in the values of metabolic parameters in a function of

hematological parameters were statistically significant. Based on the above, the link between blood count parameters that indicate inflammation and metabolic adaptations in cows in early lactation is demonstrated. In further research should examine the relationship between inflammatory and metabolic parameters.

REFERENCES

- BELIĆ, B., CINCOVIĆ, M.R., KRČMAR, L.J., VIDOVIĆ, B.: Reference values and frequency distribution of hematological parameters in cows during lactation and in pregnancy. *Contemporary agriculture*, 60:145-151, 2011.
- BELIĆ, B., CINCOVIĆ, M.R., STOJANOVIĆ, D., KOVAČEVIĆ, Z., VIDOVIĆ, B.: Morphology of erythrocyte and ketosis in dairy cows with different body condition. *Contemporary agriculture*, 59:306-311, 2010.
- BELIĆ B., CINCOVIĆ M.R., DAVIDOV I., LAKO B., POTKONJAK A., STANČIĆ I.: Periparturient hematological finding in dairy cows with uterus and udder inflammation. *Contemporary agriculture*, 61(1-2)112-118, 2012.
- CINCOVIĆ, M.R., BELIĆ, B., RADOJIĆIĆ, B., HRISTOV, S., ĐOKOVIĆ, R.: Influence of lipolysis and ketogenesis to metabolic and hematological parameters in dairy cows during periparturient period. *Acta veterinaria (Beograd)*, 62(4)429-444, 2012.
- DAVIS, A.K., MANEY, D.L., MAERZI, J.C.: The use of leukocyte profiles to measure stress in vertebrates: a review for ecologists. *Functional Ecology*, 22:760-772, 2008.
- DJOKOVIĆ R. CINCOVIĆ, M., KURCUBIC, V., PETROVIĆ, M., LALOVIĆ, M., JAŠOVIĆ, B., STANIMIROVIĆ, Z.: Endocrine and Metabolic Status of Dairy Cows during Transition Period. *Thai J. Vet. Med.*, 44(1)59-66, 2014.
- KLINKON, M., ZADNIK, T.: Dynamics of red and white blood picture in dairy cows during the periparturient period. *Comparative Hematology International*, 9:156-161, 1999.
- LATIMER, K.S., PRASSE, K.W.: *Leukocytes*. In: Duncan and Prasse's Veterinary Laboratory Medicine: Clinical Pathology. 4th ed. Ames, IA: Iowa State Press, 46-79, 2003.
- LYNCH, E.M., EARLEY, B., MCGEE, M., DOYLE, S.: Characterisation of physiological and immunological responses in beef cowsto abrupt weaning and subsequent housing. *BMC Veterinary Research*, 6:37, 2010.
- MIRZADEH, K.H., TABATABEI, S., BOJARPOUR, M., MAMOEI, M.: Comparative study of hematological parameters according strain, age, sex, physiological status and season in Iranian cattle. *Journal of Animal and Veterinary Advances*, 9(16)2123-2127, 2010.
- SATTAR A., MIRZA R.H.: Haematological parameters in exotic cows during gestation and lactation under subtropical conditions. *Pakistan Vet. J.*, 29(3)129-132, 2009.
- SORDILLO, L.M., CONTRERAS, G.A., AITKEN S.L.: Metabolic factors affecting the inflammatory response of periparturient dairy cows. *Anim Health Res Rev.*, 10(1):53-63, 2009.
- TORNQUIST S.J., RIGAS J.: Interpretation of Ruminant Leukocyte Responses. In: Schalm's veterinary hematology. 6th edition, Wiley-Blackwell, 307-313, 2010.
- WATHES, D.C., CHENG, Z., BOURNE, N., TAYLOR, V.J., COFFEY, M.P., BROTHERSTONE, S.: Differences between primiparous and multiparous dairy cows in the interrelationships between metabolic traits, milk yield and body condition score in the periparturient period. *Domestic Animal Endocrinology*, 33(2)203-225, 2007.

ISPITIVANJE VEZE IZMEĐU KRVNE SLIKE I PARAMETARA METABOLIČKOG STATUSA KRAVA U RANOJ LAKTACIJI

ZORANA KOVAČEVIĆ, MARKO R. CINCOVIĆ, BRANISLAVA BELIĆ,
DRAGICA STOJANOVIĆ, RADOJICA ĐOKOVIĆ

Izvod: Energetski metabolizam kod krava je značajno izmenjen u ranoj laktaciji, postoji povećana koncentracija BHB i bilirubina, a snižena koncentracija glukoze. Metabolizam protein je takođe izmenjen tako da je koncentracija ukupnih proteina, albumina i uree najniža u prvoj nedelji posle partusa, da bi potom lagano rasla. U peripartalnom periodu, posebno na sam dan porođaja i u prvim danima laktacije krave imaju manji broj eritrocita i nižu koncentraciju hemoglobin. Dolazi do opadanja ukupnog broja leukocita. Israživanje je izvedeno na 40 krava Holštajn-frizijske rase. Uzorci krvi su uzeti u prvoj nedelji nakon teljenja. Cilj ove studije je bio da se utvrdi veza između krvne slike i parametara metaboličkog statusa krava u ranoj laktaciji. Na osnovu statističke analize primećeno je da ne postoji veza između ukupnog broja leukocita i metaboličkog statusa krava u ranoj laktaciji. Takođe, primećeno je da krave sa višim vrednostima N:L odnosa, nižom koncentracijom hemoglobina i manjim brojem eritrocita imaju višu koncentraciju BHB, AST i TBIL i nižu koncentraciju ALB. Trend promene u vrednostima metaboličkih parametara u funkciji hematoloških parametara je statistički značajan. Navedeni parametri pokazuju da postoji veza između parametara krvne slike koji ukazuju na inflamaciju i parametara koji ukazuju na

metaboličku adaptaciju krava u ranoj laktaciji. U budućim istraživanjima treba ispitati vezu između inflamatornih i metaboličkih parametara kod krava u ranoj laktaciji.

Ključne reči: krvna slika, metabolički status, krave.

Received / *Primljen*: 03.02.2015.

Accepted / *Prihvaćen*: 16.02.2015.